

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

SPOKE 4 - Digital and Sustainable Mountain

RM6. Technological innovation and outdoor teaching in education services as a lever in multi-class schools

FINAL REPORT

Final report: A model for innovative education in mountain areas combining digital technology, environmental education and outdoor learning -Deliverable n.30-

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework - NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document has been developed within the research module “Contrast to the depopulation of mountain territories. Technological innovation on education services as a lever in multi-class schools”, which includes four tasks:

- Task 1.1 – Analysis of the use of digital teaching in multi-classes
- Task 1.2 – Analysis of the different types of digitization of educational services
- Task 1.3 – Develop a model for the use of digital innovation in the education sector according to the needs of the territories
- Task 1.4 – Connection with Nature

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The analysis considers, starting from the implementation of institutional designs, teaching models, and support services, with the use of advanced technologies, digitization of processes, of what was done during the period of the Covid-19 pandemic. The goal was to understand how to increase digitization without losing the quality of teaching, the inclusion of students at risk of dropping out, and methods of enrichment with innovative subjects (e.g sustainability, green, etc). The following activities were carried out:

- Analysis of the Italian regulatory framework for school services.
- Analysis of consistent public management models in institutions involved in educational policies.
- Analysis of innovative educational models in public institutions.
- Analysis of the regulatory frameworks for multi-class education: benchmarking in other countries with similar conditions to our country.
- Research of relevant scientific literature at the national and international levels.
- Analysis of the specific regulatory framework for educational services in the Aosta Valley Autonomous Region.
- Analysis of the social and demographic context regarding the option of multi-class education in Italy and in the sub-alpine regions.
- Detailed mapping of educational institutions in the Aosta Valley Autonomous Region.
- Development of an institutional network to establish institutional sponsorship for field research activities.
- Current analysis of the production of multi-class services:

- Analysis of the organizational design of public institutions involved in the production process.
- Analysis of the state of the art in the delivery of education services (core services) today in Valle d'Aosta and the alpine regions: competencies and roles (professional and management roles), production process (subjects and content, service structure, etc.), target users, expected and achieved outputs and outcomes.
- Analysis of the state of the art in the delivery of education services (accessory services) today in Valle d'Aosta and the alpine regions (supporting roles, etc.).
- Analysis of the state of the art in digitalization of lessons.
- Construction of a stakeholder map in the region to serve as institutional actors to engage in stakeholder analysis.
- Stakeholder engagement through workshops, interviews, and field analyses using questionnaires.
- Analysis and evaluation — through surveys of school principals, staff, teachers, and parents — of innovative teaching methods.
- Development of software prototype to support innovative teaching in primary and secondary schools.

All the phases completed, and just listed, in the project's progress were fundamental elements to define the continuation of the research which saw the development of a form of “Network analysis” in which the network system made up of educational policy actors, direct and indirect production process actors, and stakeholders with degrees of co-production of the service has been "isolated".

The valorisation of the actors involved in the public policy process, decision-making, the delivery of education services to multi-class settings and, the mapping of internal and external stakeholders related to the unique relationship between the institutional context and the production process have confirmed the relevance of the starting point of the research effort. Indeed, analysing, testing, and proposing digitalization strategies for certain educational services, starting with multi-classrooms, with a focus on evolving and evolving models—at the end of 2025, the Italian Minister of Education sanctioned, through resolutions and accelerated testing, open classroom models in multiple formats—is now a priority in our country and a preliminary formula for designing and proposing models consistent with the needs of those involved in teaching and those who benefit from them.

The final part of the research action, the one concerning the design of a prototype of an AI-based software to support innovative teaching activities in primary and secondary schools, serve as a "grounding" point for the project, reflecting on and envisioning the future of research action. The education sector and the Public Management approach are currently receiving significant attention in Italy (where the central government has proactively relaunched and regulated action on innovation in teaching, digitalization, and the use of AI, continuing into the second half of 2025,

confirming and reinforcing the Project's research principles). Furthermore, other key institutional actors, considered institutional stakeholders capable of exerting authoritative moral suasion, are also expressing their opinion on the need for innovation, investment—including economic investment—and attention to the education sector and its Public Management approaches.

Artificial Intelligence has the potential to revolutionize education by offering personalized learning experiences, automating administrative tasks, and supporting teachers in identifying student needs.

Furthermore, and above all, since the theoretical substrate to the modeling of the research framework is to bring together public institutions dealing with educational policies, end users, user needs and advanced technology, another key issue in the near future is the implementation of education policies based on the principles of equity and access: the digital divide it is still a risk and can be a significant obstacle to the equitable use of AI and technology in educational institutions and for different stakeholders.

Compared to the initial Road Map, the project was developed by adding, along the way, the final phase of building a prototype AI platform. This toolkit, initially designed for teachers—a fundamental part of the core service—but which also takes into account, within the platform itself, specific management and organizational tools to support the decisions of educational institutions and individual teachers, can be instrumental, already in the experimentation phase, in determining the degree of interaction between actors in the educational process at different levels of governance.

A) Introduction

This report presents the outcomes of the research program conducted within the framework of the PNRR project NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile, specifically within Spoke 4 - Digital and Sustainable Mountain. The study addresses a central challenge for education systems operating in mountain and sparsely populated territories: how to reconcile the structural constraints of demographic decline and territorial dispersion with the need to provide inclusive, innovative, and high-quality educational services.

The investigation has focused on the case of the Aosta Valley Autonomous Region, a context marked by distinctive institutional, cultural, and linguistic characteristics, as well as by the widespread presence of multi-class and, more recently, open classes teaching models. These models, though rooted in the history of mountain schooling, acquire renewed relevance when considered in light of contemporary organizational demands, digital transformation, and the imperatives of sustainability.

This research has been designed as a multi-year, mixed-methods program, integrating quantitative surveys, qualitative interviews, focus groups, and co-design workshops. This methodological configuration reflects a central assumption: that innovative teaching models cannot be fully understood if approached solely as pedagogical practices. Rather, they must be analysed as organizational phenomena situated within a complex institutional ecosystem, shaped by regulatory frameworks, resource configurations, and professional norms.

The project has thus engaged with schools and their actors in experimental processes of innovation, exploring how digital tools, outdoor education, and collaborative organizational models can be combined to generate new practices.

The findings discussed in this report highlight both opportunities and tensions. Multi-class and open class teaching models emerge as spaces of ambivalence: valued for their capacity to foster personalization, cooperation, and inclusion, yet also perceived as burdensome in terms of planning, workload, and training requirements. Digital technologies, while widely available, display uneven levels of integration and frequently reveal a mismatch between infrastructural investment and the development of competences. At the same time, innovative organizational forms—such as open classes—show the potential to redefine not only pedagogical processes but also the relationship between students, teachers, and school spaces.

By combining analytical depth with empirical grounding, this report aims to contribute to the broader debate on innovation in education systems operating under structural constraints. It provides evidence-based insights and managerial recommendations that can inform regional policymakers, school managers and practitioners engaged in the ongoing transformation of education in mountain areas.

B) Institutional models for education in Italy

2.1 How the education governance system works in Italy

The Italian education system, particularly at the level of primary and secondary schooling, is a complex institutional arrangement shaped by both national legislation and regional governance dynamics. Its organizational configuration reflects Italy's broader constitutional framework, where education is considered a fundamental right and a public responsibility, and where authority is shared across multiple levels of government.

At the core of the system lies the Ministero dell'Istruzione e del Merito (Ministry of Education and Merit, MIM), which provides central direction, standard-setting, and oversight. The Ministry is responsible for defining general educational objectives, establishing the national curriculum, setting minimum service levels, and ensuring overall equity and quality across the country. The Italian Constitution (Articles 33 and 34) establishes the right to education and the principles of freedom of teaching and learning, thereby framing the normative foundations of governance.

Normative framework is so defined mainly by the laws detailed below.

- Law 59/1997 (the so-called "Bassanini Law", from the surname of its proponent), that introduced the framework of school autonomy within the limits of state-defined curricula.
- The Presidential Decree 275/1999, that provided the regulatory framework for the (school autonomy (autonomia scolastica), allowing institutions to develop their own three-year educational plan (Piano Triennale dell'Offerta Formativa, PTOF).
- Subsequently, Constitutional Law 3/2001 redefined the division of powers between the State and the Regions, recognizing the latter's legislative competences in matters of education within nationally defined principles.
- Lastly, Law 53/2003 restructured cycles of education, reasserting the centrality of national curriculum guidelines.

Furthermore, later reforms (notably Law 107/2015, nicknamed "The Buona Scuola" reform, meaning Good School) emphasized teacher recruitment, professional development, digitalization, and stakeholder participation in school governance.

The governance system thus oscillates between centralization and decentralization: while the State defines general principles, essential levels of services, and curricular standards, Regions and Local Authorities have responsibilities in areas such as school building maintenance, vocational training, and certain aspects of service delivery (e.g., student transportation, canteens). Individual schools, endowed with juridical personality and managerial autonomy since 2000, occupy a hybrid institutional space: they must comply with national guidelines but can tailor educational offerings and organizational solutions to local needs.

So, the Italian education governance model can be read as a layered structure, where coercive pressures (laws and national regulations), normative elements (professional norms of teachers

and school leaders), and mimetic dynamics (local experimentation, imitation of successful practices) coexist. This creates an institutional environment characterized by complexity, negotiation, and frequent reforms that attempt to reconcile equity with territorial differentiation.

2.2 Institutional structures, actors, management and organizational models, communication

The institutional architecture of Italian primary and secondary education involves a multi-level set of actors, each with distinct roles and organizational logics.

2.2.1 Institutional structures and actors

First actor is the Ministry of Education and Merit (MIM): this is the apex institution, responsible for strategy, standards, and national policies. It operates through central departments and peripheral offices, notably the regional school offices (Uffici Scolastici Regionali, USR), which act as territorial articulations of the Ministry.

Following, the regional authorities on occasions intervene on issues such as teacher training, innovation, and European funds for education. However, greater role is played by local authorities such as Provinces/Metropolitan Cities and municipalities: the latter manage nursery schools (outside the scope here) and services like transportation and canteens for compulsory education, while the formers are responsible for maintaining and managing buildings for upper secondary schools.

Finally, any individual school (Istituti Scolastici) has legal personality and administrative autonomy. They are governed by a school manager (Dirigente Scolastico), supported by administrative staff and participatory bodies.

2.2.2 Management and organization

The managerial line of Italian schools is formally shaped by the school manager, who holds strong organizational and administrative powers. Italian school leaders operate as both managers and institutional mediators, balancing accountability to the Ministry with responsiveness to local communities. Their responsibilities include human resource management (within national recruitment frameworks), budgetary control, and organizational development.

Schools operate within a governance framework that includes participatory bodies:

- Teachers' Council (Collegio dei Docenti), that designs educational offerings and teaching innovations.
- School Council (Consiglio d'Istituto), composed of teachers, parents, students (in secondary schools), and staff, serving as a deliberative body for organizational and financial decisions.
- Executive Committee (Giunta Esecutiva), that supports the Council in implementing decisions.

This mix of managerial authority and collegial governance represents a distinctive organizational model, where formal hierarchy coexists with distributed participation.

2.2.3 Communication

Communication plays a crucial role in sustaining legitimacy within the Italian education system. At the institutional level, the Ministry disseminates policy guidelines, reforms, and curricular frameworks through official decrees, circulars, and digital platforms. Regional and local actors mediate these communications, often reinterpreting central directives in light of territorial priorities.

At the school level, communication strategies are increasingly formalized through the PTOF, which serves both as an internal planning document and as an external communication tool toward families and communities. Schools are also required to publish a self-evaluation report (Rapporto di autovalutazione) and an improvement plan, instruments designed to enhance transparency and accountability.

Digitalization has reinforced communication flows: the electronic register (Registro elettronico) has become the central interface between schools and families, ensuring daily communication on attendance, grading, and learning processes. At the same time, institutional websites, newsletters, and increasingly social media profiles extend schools' public presence and stakeholder engagement.

In conclusion, Italian schools can be seen as organizations that must simultaneously enact compliance (reporting, transparency, adherence to reforms) and construct legitimacy in their local environments. The emphasis on documents like the PTOF reflects a neo-institutional logic, where formal plans and reports are as much about signalling accountability as about driving internal change.

2.2.4 Further developments

Recent developments point to a gradual managerialization of schools, with growing emphasis on accountability, performance evaluation, and digital transparency. However, the enduring presence of collegial bodies and strong professional norms among teachers maintains a plural governance model, preventing a fully top-down managerial approach. The result is a hybrid institutional model: centrally guided, regionally mediated, and locally enacted, where organizational practices reflect both national policies and community expectations.

So, the Italian education system for primary and secondary schooling illustrates a complex interplay of centralized regulation, regional differentiation, and local autonomy. Its governance model is defined by foundational constitutional principles, key legislative milestones, and a layered distribution of competences. The institutional structures include national, regional, and local actors, with individual schools enjoying legal and organizational autonomy within the boundaries of state-defined frameworks.

In conclusion, Italian schools embody a hybrid model, where managerial authority, collegial decision-making, and communicative practices converge to sustain both efficiency and legitimacy.

C) The Aosta Valley Autonomous Region and the delivery of educational services

3.1 The Aosta Valley Autonomous Region

Aosta Valley is an autonomous region located in the northwest of Italy, bordering France and Switzerland. It is the smallest and least populated region in the country, with a population of about 125,000 inhabitants.

It is necessary to underline that there are institutional reasons why the structures responsible who define educational policies and produce and provide final public educational services in the Aosta Valley Region take on unique and specific characteristics: among them, an institutional design centralized at the regional level for policies and decentralized at the of scholastic institutes that take specific decisions autonomously on the production of services stands out.

The Aosta Valley Autonomous Region enjoys a special statute that grants it a high degree of autonomy, recognized by the Italian Constitution and the Special Statute for Aosta Valley, approved in 1948. This autonomy also extends to educational policies, allowing the region to manage and organize the educational system in a way that differs from other Italian regions.

The Region has exclusive legislative powers regarding the organization of school services. This includes the ability to adapt national curricula to local needs; in other words, the Regional Council of Aosta Valley has the ability to introduce specific subjects and modify the content of mandatory subjects to reflect the local reality and cultural traditions of the region.

One of the most distinctive aspects of the Aosta Valley school system is the emphasis on bilingualism. In Aosta Valley, teaching is conducted in both Italian and French, in line with the region's cultural and historical tradition. French is not only a school subject but also a genuine medium of instruction in various disciplines. This approach aims to preserve and promote the cultural and linguistic identity of the region.

3.2 A complex management situation

In the educational system of Aosta Valley Autonomous Region, a key function is carried out by the Superintendency of Studies. The Superintendency is a department that operates under the Assessorate for Cultural Heritage and Activities, Educational System, and Intergenerational Policies.

The Superintendent of Studies coordinates, from a technical perspective, activities related to regional educational policy, in line with national guidelines and regulations.

During the school year, periodic meetings are held with representatives from the Ministry of Education and Merit (MIM), particularly concerning the National Evaluation System and digital platforms aimed at bringing schools, students, and families closer together (The School for Everyone - Unified Platform).

However, the principle of the autonomy of educational institutions (administrative, didactic, and organizational) is fully respected, as regulated by DPR 275/99 and Regional Law 19/2000, always in compliance with the general educational standards issued by the State and the Region.

It should also be noted that within the Department of Structural Policies and European Affairs of the specific department named European Affairs, Innovation, PNRR, and National Policies for the Mountain, which deals with European issues and the management of funding, there is a structure for Programming the European Social Fund and managing co-financed projects in the field of education, with an office dedicated to co-financed education projects.

Furthermore, educational institutions directly benefit from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza-PNRR, 2021-2026) and PON (Operational Programmes) funds.

Lastly, during the implementation of the PNRR, the Superintendency also has managed some PNRR funding related to scholarships to ensure the right to education.

3.2 Educational institutions in Aosta Valley

Overall, in Aosta Valley there are eighteen public primary and lower secondary grade educational institutions; seven upper secondary level schools; and twelve paritary schools, some of which include multiple grades.

The mapping of the educational institutions in the territory reveals elements of complexity concerning the organizational and managerial situation.

There is a multitude of educational institutions that integrate primary and lower secondary grade, often with multiple sites distributed across several municipalities. Nevertheless, upper secondary schools are less widespread across the Region's territory.

It should be noted that several educational institutions in the examined area are led by an acting head. This is, however, not a specific characteristic of Aosta Valley but is quite common in Italian schools, which often suffer from a chronic understaffing issue.

Furthermore, there are issues connected to the morphological context of the Aosta Valley territory which is a mountainous territory limited in terms of size but with valleys and municipalities where schools are located which require particular attention from the point of view of resource planning and provision of the educational service. Moreover, due to the limited population (which is also undergoing a significant decline), many schools adopt the multi-class model, thus forming classes with students of different ages; this implies planning and delivering activities differently from schools where teaching takes place in single-grade classes.

A detailed mapping of Aosta Valley educational institutions has been included in deliverables n. 25 and 26.

D) Innovation in digital media and education

4.1 Regulatory Framework

Digital innovation in Italian education system has seen, over the past two decades, broad changes. National and European policy frameworks have attempted to align the education system with broader digital transformation agendas. The Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027) and the DigComp framework have provided common standards and orientations for member states, including Italy. Domestically, the Ministry of Education and Merit has launched successive strategic initiatives, such as the National Digital School Plan (PNSD, 2015, updated 2021), which established digitalization as a transversal priority across all levels of schooling. Complementary regulations, such as guidelines for digital textbooks, the introduction of the electronic register, and requirements for institutional transparency through online platforms, have progressively redefined both pedagogical practices and organizational routines.

These frameworks create a layered governance environment in which schools must interpret and enact digital directives within their local contexts. The National Recovery and Resilience Plan has further accelerated this process, channeling significant financial resources toward infrastructure, teacher training, and digital inclusion, while also imposing accountability mechanisms. However, the regulatory approach often reflects a tension between symbolic compliance, through the formal adoption of digital plans and reports, and substantive organizational change. Schools thus operate within a “compliance-innovation paradox,” where the need to adhere to centrally defined frameworks coexists with pressures to generate locally meaningful innovation.

4.2 Skills, tools and techniques

The adoption of digital technologies in Italian primary and secondary schools has expanded the repertoire of organizational and pedagogical practices, creating new demands for skills and competences. Teachers and school managers are increasingly expected to cultivate digital pedagogical competence, combining subject-specific knowledge with the ability to integrate digital tools into learning processes. Programs such as DIGITAL SKILLS for Teachers (Docenti Innovatori) and the diffusion of European certification systems (e.g., ECDL/ICDL, DigCompEdu) highlight a move toward formal recognition of digital competence as a core professional standard.

Schools are currently experimenting with a wide array of tools and techniques: learning management systems (LMS) such as Google Classroom or Moodle; synchronous and asynchronous platforms for blended learning; adaptive testing and assessment systems; and collaborative tools that restructure classroom dynamics. The forced acceleration during the

COVID-19 pandemic institutionalized many of these practices, normalizing hybrid and remote modalities. Beyond classroom practices, digitalization has reshaped school management through the pervasive use of the electronic register, digital administrative workflows, and data-driven self-evaluation instruments.

The emerging picture is one of hybridization: traditional didactic approaches coexist with digitally mediated practices, and analogue governance logics are intertwined with algorithmic forms of coordination and communication. This hybridity requires not only technical competences but also organizational learning capacities, enabling schools to reflect, adapt, and reconfigure routines. Digital tools act as both resources and institutional scripts: they provide opportunities for efficiency and innovation, but also embed normative expectations about transparency, accountability, and modernity. Consequently, digital innovation in education is not reducible to technology adoption, as it requires a deeper redefinition of professional roles, workflows and institutional and communicative practices within the Italian school system.

E) Biophilia driven environmental education

The global environmental challenges of our century require a new ecological awareness, which can be achieved with robust environmental education that leverages our evolutionary history and offers adequate tools for interpreting the crisis. Experimental research has revealed that humans have an innate tendency to love life (biophilia) and that the fascination that wild Nature exerts on our psyche is a powerful stimulator of our biophilia. Stimulating biophilia can foster a deeper affiliation with Nature, which, in turn, is the basis for the development of naturalistic intelligence, the primary human resource for addressing environmental crises.

5.1 Building Naturalistic Intelligence

Biophilia is a predisposition to learn from natural environments based on the constructs of fascination and affiliation (Wilson, 2002). Rapid and effective learning gave our ancestors an evolutionary advantage, and it is therefore likely that fascination and affiliation have consolidated over time as the psychobiological potential of naturalistic intelligence (Barbiero & Berto, 2021).

5.1.1 From biophilia to the "environmentally concerned" personality

Howard Gardner defined naturalistic intelligence as the ability to "recognize flora and fauna, make other consequent distinctions in the natural world, and use this capacity productively" (Gardner, 1995). Gardner originally identified seven modes of intelligence in his theory of multiple intelligences (Gardner, 1983). Only fifteen years later did he recognize, and subsequently integrate, naturalistic intelligence into his theory (Gardner, 1999). Gardner believes that naturalistic intelligence is an expression of "what Wilson called 'biophilia.'" According to Gardner, "the naturalist's intelligence is at home in the world of living organisms and may possess the talent to care for, tame, or subtly interact with various living creatures" (Gardner 1999, p. 49). The ability to "care for" and "subtly interact" are manifestations of the awareness of having an affective and emotional bond with Nature and correspond to Wilson's affiliation. Fundamentally, naturalistic intelligence fosters affiliation, which, in turn, strengthens the desire to know Nature

and prepares for new experiences, in a virtuous cycle of experience-reflection-experience. Gardner emphasizes that "biologists' biographies routinely document an early fascination with plants and animals" (Gardner, 1999, p. 50, emphasis added). Although there is no evidence in the literature of a relationship between attentional regeneration and naturalistic intelligence, biologists' biographies show that an early "fascination (fundamental for regeneration)" is crucial for the development of naturalistic intelligence. Finally, Gardner observes that the biographies of famous naturalists - such as, for example, Rachel Carson (1962) or E.O. Wilson (1994) - show that mature naturalistic intelligence tends to be sensitive to environmental conservation, strengthening the individual's pro-environmental behavior. In 2017, Rita Berto and I proposed a model that correlated affiliation (measured with the Connectedness to Nature Scale, CNS), fascination (measured with the Perceived Restorativeness Scale, PRS), environmental knowledge, and commitment to the environment. The model was designed to highlight how pro-environmental behavior could be influenced by the cognitive and affective constructs of biophilia (Berto & Barbiero, 2017a). Subsequently, we proposed a revision of that model, replacing environmental knowledge with naturalistic intelligence, and proposing fascination as a motivator for pro-environmental behavior (Barbiero & Berto, 2021).

Figure 1. Model linking the two biophilic constructs - fascination and affiliation - (in green), naturalistic intelligence, environmental concern, and pro-environmental behavior (Barbiero & Berto, 2021).

5.1.2 Biophilic Environmental Qualities for Outdoor Education

Cultivating intelligence always requires an appropriate environment. This is especially true for naturalistic intelligence, which requires a natural environment that stimulates biophilia. It is important to identify the qualities that stimulate biophilia, or the "biophilic qualities" of an environment. The term "biophilic qualities" refers to the set of physical, aesthetic, and functional characteristics of an environment that are perceived as regenerative. We know that the regenerative power of an environment corresponds to fascination, and therefore to one of the fundamental constructs of biophilia. To this end, Rita Berto and I have developed a tool, the Biophilic Quality Index (BQI, Berto & Barbiero, 2017b), to synthetically measure The characteristics of an environment as a function of the regenerative factors described in the Attention

Regeneration Theory (Kaplan, 1995). When we sought to investigate whether there is a correlation between fascination and affiliation, we discovered that the correlation exists and is mediated by the “biophilic quality” of the environment. We compared four different natural parks to which we assigned two levels of “biophilic quality” (high or low) based on two factors: distance from the subject's residence (being away) and regenerative potential (fascination) assessed with the Recreation Opportunity Spectrum, a quality assessment system for natural parks (Clark and Stankey, 1979). We assessed the affiliation with Nature (with the CNS) and the fascination (with the PRS) of each visitor to each park. The study found that when the environment is characterized by low biophilic quality (e.g., an urban park) and the visitor has a low level of affiliation with Nature, the environment is perceived as highly regenerative. Conversely, when the visitor has a high level of affiliation with Nature, the environment characterized by low biophilic quality is perceived as less regenerative. Only when the environment is characterized by high biophilic quality (e.g., a nature reserve) are subjects with a high level of affiliation with Nature able to fully perceive the regenerative potential of the wild environment. Subjects with high affiliation appear to have a greater ability to discern regenerative environments. Feeling strongly connected to Nature (affiliation) makes one more sensitive to the regenerative power (fascination) of an environment and allows one to recognize environments with the best biophilic qualities.

5.2 Outdoor Sensitive Dance to strengthen children's biophilia

Based on our experience with experimental biophilia, in 2023 the Environmental and Nature Education Research Group at the University of Valle d'Aosta (GREEN-Univda) launched a project to strengthen children's connection to nature through the implementation of Sensitive Dance.

5.2.1 The Sensitive Dance Teacher Network

The core of the project is the creation of a network of approximately ten teachers aged 30 to 55, drawn from primary schools in Piedmont and Valle d'Aosta. These teachers, with a mix of humanistic and scientific expertise, were selected for their dedication to outdoor biophilic education and learning. To implement this network, GREEN-Univda has developed a work program based on Sensitive Dance. We hypothesized that this practice, by primarily targeting kinesthetic intelligence, could stimulate not only bodily and sensorial aspects, but also emotional and cognitive aspects, such as movement organization, sequence memory, and spatial orientation, thus improving biophilia.

5.2.2 Research methodology

The project aimed to enhance children's connection with nature through outdoor activities, using Sensitive Dance as a preparatory action. To measure the degree of connection with nature, empathy toward it, and affective attitude, GREEN-Univda chose three psychometric scales: the CNS, the Dispositional Empathy with Nature (DEN), and the Children's Affective Attitude towards Nature (CAAN).

5.2.3 Experimental design

Fifth-grade primary school students were the focus of experimental observations. We established an experimental group that participated in Sensitive Dance sessions and compared them with a

control group, which attended physical education lessons. Both groups completed CNS tests before the start of the sessions and after a five-week period.

5.2.4 Preliminary results

The initial activities allowed us to test the methodology both in schools inside and outside the Gran Paradiso National Park (PNGP). Despite significant environmental differences, no significant differences emerged in the initial results. We therefore hypothesized that a key factor is the continuity of activities carried out in contact with nature. This would confirm the experimental observations conducted in the Bracing Biophilia project, which revealed that outdoor activities are effective in enhancing feelings of affiliation with nature only if they are offered consistently (Barbiero et al., 2021). Discussions with teachers highlighted the need for more continuous planning of activities and more tools for Nature education, emphasizing the importance of balancing classroom and outdoor activities.

5.3 Conclusions

Biophilia is an innate predisposition to learn from natural environments and is the psychobiological basis of naturalistic intelligence. Biophilia is based on the constructs of fascination and affiliation. The feeling of affiliation with Nature can only grow if contact with Nature is maintained continuously in high quality biophilic environments. An interesting way to maintain continuous contact with Nature is to use eco-mindfulness techniques.

F) Research: structure, actors involved, and road map

6.1 The research. Methods, tools, techniques, actors and road map over the three years of research

This research program has investigated the organizational, pedagogical, and technological dynamics of multi-class and open classes teaching in Aosta Valley primary and secondary schools. Its core objective is to assess how digital innovation, managerial practices, and institutional frameworks shape the functioning of these models, and to generate recommendations for policymakers, school leaders, and teachers. To achieve this, the project adopted a mixed-methods design developed over three years, combining surveys, interviews, focus groups, and co-design workshops.

The research was conducted by the academic research team through the collaboration of regional authorities, school managers, teachers and local communities. The roadmap was structured into three phases: baseline data collection and analysis; in-depth qualitative inquiry and pilot interventions; and consolidation with validation workshops and final recommendations. This architecture ensured both methodological robustness and results' relevance.

6.2 Objectives and research questions

The research has been carried out with three sets of objectives.

First, the research team proceeded to map the organizational and pedagogical practices of multi-class and open classes teaching, and to identify institutional and organizational conditions and actors enabling or constraining digital innovation.

Furthermore, the research team aimed at designing, testing, and refining managerial and organizational models that can be integrated into schools' strategic planning documents as the best choice to fit with the pedagogical models of schools placed in little and dispersedly populated areas.

The final objective was to provide evidence-based guidance for regional authorities and the Ministry of Education in balancing infrastructural investment, training programs, and institutional reforms.

The research team began by investigating how multi-class arrangements are organized and managed in Aosta Valley schools; during the study, however, the open classes teaching model, as implemented in Aosta, was pointed out as a best practice.

So, the research team identified a package of research questions:

- What are the experiences, perceptions, and expectations of teachers, principals and pupils' parents regarding these models?
- What role do digital tools and techniques play in enabling or limiting their effectiveness?
- How do institutional frameworks, professional norms, and resource conditions interact in shaping innovation trajectories?

Multi-class and open classes models, even if not completely an innovation (as in scarcely populated areas the multi-class teaching model has a long history), require organizational adaptation and new forms of coordination. Digital tools are analyzed not simply as neutral instruments, but as socio-material artefacts that carry institutional expectations and reshape communication, accountability, and teaching practices.

6.3 Research Design

The project adopted a mixed-methods approach, structured in sequential - and sometimes overlapping - phases. Quantitative surveys provide broad mapping of attitudes, practices, and priorities, while qualitative interviews and focus groups generate in-depth understanding of practice, routines, and innovations opportunities. Workshops and pilot interventions serve as experimental spaces to co-design and validate practical solutions.

This design responds to the complexity of the object of study: multi-class and open classes teaching is not only a pedagogical phenomenon but also an organizational and institutional one, embedded in local communities and governance frameworks.

6.4 Methods and techniques

6.4.1 Standard techniques

A structured online survey was administered to teachers, school managers, staff and students' parents across schools with and without multi-class or open classes experience. The instrument covered institutional profiles, experiences with multi-class and/or open classes, perceptions of benefits and difficulties, technology adoption, and managerial needs. Data analysis focused on descriptive statistics, cross-tabulations, and ranking exercises to identify priorities and divergences.

6.4.1 Non-standard techniques

Semi-structured interviews, administered during on-fields research activities, targeted school managers and experienced multi-class teachers. Focus groups gathered school managers and teachers with different levels of experience, fostering peer discussion and collective reflection. Workshops with teachers and principals were used to outline new practices, pilot digital pedagogical models, and discuss how they may be integrated into schools' strategic planning. Risks such as limited connectivity, high staff turnover, or time constraints for teachers were anticipated and mitigated through flexible scheduling, digital tools, and close collaboration with principals.

These settings provided iterative feedback loops, allowing organizational models to be tested, discussed, and validated.

6.5 Actors Involved

The project mobilized a multi-level actor network:

The academic research team was responsible for design, analysis, and carrying out the research activities. Regional authorities and educational officers first outlined the key framework of Aosta Valley educational system and then provided legitimacy, access for research, and policy linkage. School managers represent key organizational actors and gatekeepers, mediating between policy, practice and civil society expectations.

Teachers have been recognized as central respondents, informants, and co-designers of new practices.

This architecture ensures triangulation of perspectives and embeds research into the institutional ecology of the Aosta Valley school system.

6.6 Data Governance and Ethics

All data collection procedures followed GDPR standards and ensure anonymity, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Consent forms and information sheets were provided, and specific attention was paid to the handling of data indirectly related to minors.

6.6 Roadmap for the three years of research

Year 1 — Mapping of research environment: legislative framework, actors and key topics. Deployment of the first survey and initial statistical analysis.

Year 2 — In-depth inquiry with on-field visit, interviews and focus groups, followed by second survey.

Year 3 — Consolidation and validation: development of a software dedicated to supporting innovative teaching models, final reporting, policy recommendations, and dissemination.

6.6.1 Preparatory activities

The research module began with a comprehensive analysis of the institutional context and the regulatory frameworks governing multi-class education in Italy and particularly in Aosta Valley. A key part of this phase was a consultation with the Superintendent of Studies for the Aosta Valley Autonomous Region, Dr. Marina Fey, which served as a crucial step in mapping regional school institutions and key stakeholders; the Superintendent provided materials that the researchers used to refine their understanding of the management processes of the education sector in the target territory.

Subsequently, a comprehensive mapping of the educational institutions in the area was carried out, identifying their locations, contact points, school managers, organizational size, and staffing levels.

6.6.2 First survey phase

This phase focused on tailoring, validating and administering a survey conceived to investigate the use of multi-class teaching models, distinguishing between institutions that have already experimented with these models and those that have not.

The questionnaire was designed as the first phase of field research to create the conditions for stakeholder engagement and define a managerial approach to public decisions in the education sector. This phase focused on the 18 public primary and lower secondary schools in the area that were part of the sample. The questionnaire was aimed at school principals, but with the possibility of also involving teachers. It was designed with a dual response path depending on whether the institution had or had not experimented with multi-class teaching models. The sections of the survey aimed to understand the advantages and disadvantages of multi-class teaching, the managerial, administrative, and technological tools needed to support it, and the multi-class models that could be most enhanced. The goal was to sequence the research lines based on the

experiences of those who had already experimented, and then to build the foundation for the subsequent investigation phase.

The survey explored a series of crucial aspects, asking school managers to evaluate the potential advantages and disadvantages of multi-class teaching, such as cooperative learning, the personalization of study plans, intergenerational relationships, and the challenges related to teacher workload and technology management.

Furthermore, the questionnaire asked respondents to rank the importance of different management areas necessary for offering an ideal educational service related to the multi-class model, including curriculum planning, resource management, teacher training, and parental involvement. The survey also investigated which technological tools (mobile devices, LMS platforms, virtual reality, educational robotics) can be most supportive in this context. Finally, the questionnaire asked to identify which multi-class model (multi-age, unified, or combined) would be most suitable for their institution.

This first survey was integrated with a second one, similar to the first, but focused on the open classroom teaching method, which the research team identified as a key issue immediately after the first survey.

6.6.3 Second survey phase

The second survey phase utilized a questionnaire to gather feedback from various roles, including teachers, administrative staff, and parents.

First, it was decided, to respect the most rigorous methodological canon possible, to keep both the structure of the sections of the questionnaire and the questions asked similar. Emblematically, in fact, the option of allowing maximum comparability between the responses of the school managers of the educational institutions and the primary stakeholders was favored. Firstly, and to mediate between the scientific principle of maximum comparability with that of the necessary adaptation required by the orientation of the questionnaire to other actors, the questions were modulated considering that they were directed at three different stakeholders. However, it is essential to point out that the questionnaire was expanded with the inclusion of the management, organizational and teaching methods of the open classes.

The survey explored opinions on whether the multi-class model has fostered greater cooperative learning, personalization of study plans, and intergenerational relationships. It also assessed if the model has enabled teachers to be more creative and feel more satisfied with their work. Conversely, the survey investigated potential challenges, such as learning difficulties, the burden of teaching and planning, and the need for differentiated teaching competencies. The questionnaire also sought to understand the perceived importance of different management areas (e.g., curriculum planning, resource management, teacher training) and the most useful technological tools for multi-class settings, ranging from mobile devices and LMS platforms to AI, VR, and educational robotics.

The questionnaire was submitted to teachers, officials and parents of pupils of the following educational institutions, that were selected for this and the subsequent phases of the research:

- Eugenia Martinet of Aosta;
- Abbé Tréves of Saint Vincent;
- Emilio Reinotti of Gressoney
- Valdigne Mt. Blanc of Morgex;
- Emile Lexert of Aosta;
- M. Ida Viglino of Villeneuve;
- Unité des Communes Valdôtaines Grand Combin of Gignod;
- Ottavio Jacquemet of Verres.

G) Phase-by-phase results

7.1 Illustration of the results of interviews, questionnaires, and workshops conducted

The results presented here stem from the sequential application of surveys, interviews, focus groups, and workshops. They are structured according to the project's phases and integrate multiple sources of evidence. The focus is on understanding how multi-class and open classes models operate in practice, how digital innovation interacts with them, what managerial and organizational implications emerge and how these innovative teaching methods may be improved with the implementation of specially dedicated digital tools.

7.1.1 Mapping of educational services in Aosta Valley Autonomous Region

The mapping of educational services in the study area revealed a diverse landscape, with numerous schools integrating primary and lower secondary levels, often distributed across multiple sites.

The detailed mapping presented in Deliverable 26, showing the situation in school year 2023-2024., that is the first year of this research, is inserted in the table below.

Year 2023/2024									
Name	Grade	School name and/or place	Alumns	Classes (mono)	Multi-classes	Total classes	Teachers (common)	Teachers (support)	Staff
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA SAN FRANCESCO - Aosta - School head: Francesco Lo Baido	Primary	P.zza San Francesco	205	11		11	18	8.5	
	Lower secondary					12	30	9	
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'SAINT-ROCH' - Aosta - School head: Luca Barbieri	Primary	Quartiere Dora	210			0	18	6.5	7
		Ponte di Pietra				0			
	Lower secondary	Corso Ivrea	214			0	26	4	
	Primary	Viale della Pace	65	5		5	21.5	12.5	8

ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA LUIGI EINAUDI - Aosta - School head: Gabriella Sottile	Primary	Luigi Einaudi - Porossan	158	10		10			
	Lower secondary	Viale della Pace	274	13		13	31	5	
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'EMILE LEXERT' - Aosta - School head: Cristiana Marchesini	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA QUARTIERE COGNE	65	5		5	24	13	7
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA RAMIRES	158	10		10			
	Lower secondary	SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO "EMILE LEXERT"	157	9		9	29	10	
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'EUGENIA MARTINET' - Aosta - School head: Federico Marchetti	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI SAINT MARTIN - "GIOVANNI PEZZOLI"	191	10		10	21	8	8
	Lower secondary	SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO 'JEAN-BAPTISTE CERLOGNE'	300	14		14	52	10	
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'VALDIGNE MONT-BLANC' - Morgex - School head: Mikaela Bois	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI LA SALLE	78	5		5	34	6	9
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI COURMAYEUR	107	5		5			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI MORGEX	86	5		5			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI PRÉ-ST-DIDIER	23		2	2			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA "LUCIA COLLOMB" - LA THUILE	29		2	2			
	Lower secondary	SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO COURMAYEUR	110	6		6	43	10	
		SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO MORGEX	136	9		9			
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA JEAN-BAPTISTE CERLOGNE' - St. Pierre - School head: Gabriella Sottile (acting)	Primary	St. Pierre	401	27		27	42	12	6
		Aymavilles				0			
		Saint-Nicolas				0			
		Sarre				0			
		Sarre				0			
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'MARIA IDA VIGLINO' - Villeneuve - School head: Emanuela Bobbio (acting)	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA D' ARVIER	41	5		5	29	4	8
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI COGNE	45	3	1	4			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI VALSAVARENCHÉ	3		1	1			

		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI VILLENEUVE	28	4		4			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI INTROD	37	1	2	3			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI RHEMES SAINT GEORGES	7		1	1			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI VALGRISENCHÉ	6		1	1			
	Lower secondary	SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO "MARIA IDA VIGLINO"	253	12		12	48	6	
		SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO - SEDE ASSOCIATA DI COGNÉ	26	1	1	2			
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA UNITÉ DES COMMUNES VALDÔTAINES GRAND COMBIN - Gignod - School head: Emanuela Bobbio	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI DOUES	20		2	2	37	4	8
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI GIGNOD - VARINEY	47	3	1	4			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI OYACE	16		2	2			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI ROISAN	20		2	2			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI ST. RHEMY-EN-BOSSÉS	32	1	2	3			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA GIGNOD - CAPOLUOGO	89	5		5			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA VALPELLINE	18		2	2			
	Lower secondary	SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO DI GIGNOD - VARINEY	150	8		8	22	5	
UNITÉ DES COMMUNES VALDÔTAINES MONT EMILIUS T' - Nus - School head: Francesco Lo Baido (acting)	Primary	St. Marcel	47			0	25	9	
		Nus	132			0			
	Fénis	71			0				
Lower secondary	Nus					22	7		
UNITÉ DES COMMUNES VALDÔTAINES MONT EMILIUS 2' - Quart - School head: Elena Maria Grosso	Primary	Brissogne	40	1	2	3	35	8.5	
		Saint-Christophe	68			0			
		Saint-Christophe	89			0			
		Quart	159	9		9			
	Lower secondary	Quart	235			0	25	7	
UNITÉ DES COMMUNES	Primary	Charvensod				0	35	7.5	15
		Gressan Chevrot				0			

VALDÔTAINES MONT EMILIUS 3' - Charvensod - School head: Stefania Nappo		Jovençon				0	30	5					
		Gressan				0							
		Charvensod				0							
		Pollein				0							
	Lower secondary	Charvensod				0							
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'ABBE' PROSPER DUC' - Chatillon - School head: Maria Giovanna Bonvicini	Primary	Verrayes	30	3		3	31	7					
		Verrayes Capoluogo	19	2		2							
		Pontey	16	2		2							
		Chatillon	31	3		3							
		Chambave	46	4		4							
	Chatillon	119	9		9								
	Lower secondary	Chatillon	154	9		9				22	5		
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'ABBÉ J.M. TRÈVES' - St. Vincent - School head: Antonietta Dallou	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI ANTEY-ST-ANDRÉ	26			2	35	5	7				
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI SAINT-VINCENT - MORON	44	3		1				4			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI TORGNON	27			2				2			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI VALTOURNENCHE - BREUIL	34			2				2			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI VALTOURNENCHE - CAPOLUOGO	46	1		2				3			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI SAINT- VINCENT - CAPOLUOGO	103	6						6			
	Lower secondary	SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO - SEDE ASSOCIATA DI VALTOURNENCHE	75	4						4	48	5	
		SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO - SEDE PRINCIPALE DI SAINT- VINCENT	155	8						8			
	ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'Luigi Barone' - Verres - School head: Luca Barbieri (acting)	Primary	Challand-Saint- Victor							0	18	2	
			Challand-Saint- Anselme							0			
Ayas						0							
Lower secondary		Verres				0							
		Brusson				0	32						
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA OTTAVIO JACQUEMET - Verres - School head: Giovanni Peduto	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA "LUCIO DUC" - ARNAD	57	3		1	42	7	7				
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI CHAMPDEPRAZ - FABBRICA	18	0		2				2			

		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI EMARÈSE	14	0	1	1			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI ISSOGNE	52	3	1	4			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI MONTJOVET - CAPOLUOGO	69	5		5			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI VERRÈS	97	7		7			
UNITÉ DES COMMUNES VALDÔTAINES MONT ROSE A' - Pont St. Martin - School head: Stefania Girodo Grant	Primary		43	3	1	4	22	3	16
			33	3	2	5			
			64	3	1	4			
			8		1	1			
	Lower secondary		267	13		13	45	7	
ISTITUZIONE SCOLASTICA 'ELIO REINOTTI'	Primary	SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI FONTAINEMORE	21		2	2	46	5	6
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI GRESSONEY LA TRINITÉ	13		2	2			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI GRESSONEY SAINT-JEAN	32	1	2	3			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI ISSIME GABY	19		2	2			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI PONT-SAINT-MARTIN	105	6		6			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA DI PONT-SAINT-MARTIN FRAZ. PRATI NUOVI	60	4		4			
		SCUOLA PRIMARIA PERLOZ	28	1	2	3			
	Lower secondary	SCUOLA SECONDARIA DI PRIMO GRADO DI GRESSONEY-SAINT-JEAN	46	3		3	14	1	
							1052.5	224.5	
Total			5.532	318	53	371	1.277		112

Data differs slightly depending on the source, but the total population of primary and lower secondary grade schools of Aosta Valley at the time was estimated to be around 5500 students, 1300 teachers and 110 officers and staff members.

7.1.2 First survey results

The survey was completed by the deadline of September 30th. In a second phase, after acquiring the possibility of receiving new responses, the questionnaire was reopened, concluding the survey on October 6th; the data presented here refer to both survey phases collectively.

In line with a socio-technical systems perspective, the survey results reveal a structurally ambivalent set of attitudes toward multi-class teaching models. While respondents consistently valued these arrangements for their potential to foster cooperative learning, curriculum personalization, and a sense of community, they simultaneously highlighted significant challenges related to increased teacher workload and the imperative for specialized pedagogical competences. This ambivalence underscores that the perceived value of multi-class teaching is contingent upon the availability of robust organizational support systems.

From a managerial and pedagogical standpoint, the findings clearly prioritize teacher training, equitable resource allocation, and inclusion strategies as fundamental pillars for successful implementation.

The data further suggests a pragmatic, rather than aspirational, approach to technology adoption.

The highest priority is placed on foundational digital infrastructure, such as reliable devices and learning platforms, which directly addresses immediate operational needs. In contrast, more advanced and potentially disruptive technologies like AI and virtual reality (VR) are seen as less critical for daily teaching practices.

Collectively, these results illuminate a critical organizational gap: while the value proposition of multi-class models is recognized, there is a clear and pressing need for strategic investment not only in hardware but, more importantly, in the development of human and organizational capabilities to effectively integrate these models within the broader educational system.

7.1.3 Workshop and focus group summary

In preparation for the second phase of the research, the results of the first survey were shared and discussed with the stakeholders in two moments which had different specificities.

The first was a workshop, held online on January 15, 2024, from 10.30 am to 12.30 pm, which saw the participation of the regional superintendent of studies, and various school heads of the local institutions involved in the research. This allowed the team of the project to discuss the results of the first phase and collect observations and reflections from the participants.

The second occasion was a focus group, held at University of Aosta Valley on February 1, 2024, that was structured to go more in depth and to firmly engage in the research the primary stakeholders, and which provided valuable qualitative insights.

Overall, the qualitative data collected in these two activities both confirmed and enriched the quantitative survey findings

Participants highlighted a dual perception of multi-class models, viewed as both a last resort to avoid school closures and a potential source of educational challenges. On one hand, educators

acknowledged its pedagogical value, particularly its capacity to foster student autonomy and social skills through peer tutoring and collaborative learning. On the other hand, these benefits were frequently offset by the significant burden of preparing differentiated lesson materials and effectively managing the heterogeneity of student groups, underscoring a critical gap between pedagogical potential and organizational reality.

A significant concern was the lack of continuous training and adequate support for teachers, particularly substitutes, in managing multi-class dynamics. Furthermore, participants emphasized the need for a paradigm shift toward student autonomy and new pedagogical models, rather than a mere transfer of traditional teaching to a digital medium. They also suggested refinements to the survey questions on digital evaluation tools, as some terms were found to be misleading.

7.1.4 Second survey results

A total of 583 responses were collected from 350 parents, 214 teachers and 19 administrative officials and staff members.

The schools in which the questionnaire was administered have a combined population of 3419 students, 623 teachers and 60 officers and staff members. This implies that the sample that responded to the questionnaire corresponds to circa 5.1% of parents, 34.3% of teachers and 31.7% of officers and staff members working or involved in the primary and lower secondary grade schools of Aosta Valley that were selected for this second phase of research.

Here are reported the results that the research team recognizes as the most interesting.

Regarding the influence of innovative teaching models on the use of new technologies by teachers (question 3.14), it is noted that the answers for all categories aggregate around neutrality, with a tendency towards a favourable response (about 30-50% in favour vs 10-25% against).

When we move to consider different teaching models, we notice that the open classes teaching model shows a more positive evaluation. About 50% of respondents emphasize that open classes models have allowed teachers to make greater use of new technologies and only less than 10% has a negative opinion.

Question 3.14

This analysis also considers differences between teachers and technical staff on one hand and parents on the other hand; interestingly, the evaluations of the two groups are very comparable. A similar arrangement of responses is visible regarding the question on the ease of use of new technologies by students in the context of innovative teaching models (question 3.15): the share of respondents with a positive evaluation range from 20 to 40 per cent, while that with negative evaluation ranges from 10 to 30 per cent. Also in this case, the open classes teaching model shows a more positive evaluation.

Question 3.15

In this survey, the technological tools that offer greater support in innovative teaching models (questions 6.1-6.11) were also examined. Mobile devices, artificial intelligence, educational robotics, and educational apps are the tools that received higher ranking evaluations. However, notable differences emerged between teachers and parents in this regard. Teachers ranked mobile devices first, whereas parents ranked artificial intelligence as their top choice. When comparing the multi-grade teaching model to the open classes teaching model, it appears that the latter benefits more from mobile devices, while the former can leverage a broader combination of technological tools such as artificial intelligence, mobile devices, and educational apps.

Questions 6.1-6.11

Lastly, the research conducted multivariate analysis, employing certain Q3 variables as dependent variables and we included as regressors Q3.14 and Q3.15, which gauge the effectiveness of innovative teaching models in integrating new technologies. The regressions revealed positive and significant coefficients, indicating that when respondents perceive innovative teaching models as facilitating the adoption and utilization of new technologies, there is a beneficial impact on both student and teacher performance.

In other words, when new technologies are embraced within innovative teaching models, these models become more efficacious in enhancing student and teacher performance. This finding holds particular significance as it directs our attention towards harnessing new technologies to bolster the effectiveness of innovative teaching models.

A further online workshop was held in October 2024 to share and discuss these results with the Superintendent and the school managers of the selected educational institutions.

7.1.5 Research limitations

The results reflect the specific context of schools included in the sample, with potential self-selection biases. Future research could broaden the geographic scope and include longitudinal student outcome data.

7.2 Open classes: a discovery made along the way

As mentioned before, during the fieldwork phase, the research team identified an interim finding of particular relevance: the importance of the open classes teaching model implemented in two of the schools in Aosta included in the study. This model, characterized by the flow of students across traditional class boundaries, was observed to facilitate differentiated learning paths and to enhance collaborative practices among students and teachers. Beyond its pedagogical dimension, the open classes arrangement also demonstrated organizational value, as it required the development of new routines for coordination, joint planning, and the management of shared spaces: this in fact changes the relationship between students and the school spaces, which are reorganized and specialized according to the activities carried out within them.

H) Valorisation of results and a new model of digital innovation for open classroom: an AI-enhanced platform for personalized teaching in open classes

8.1 Introduction

The transformation of contemporary educational ecosystems increasingly relies on digital infrastructures capable of supporting differentiated, adaptive, and inclusive learning pathways. One of the most significant innovations in this domain is the emergence of platforms capable of automatically transforming teaching materials into differentiated versions adapted to diverse student profiles. Within this context, the Open Classroom platform presented in this section represents an innovative technological solution conceived to support the organizational teaching model of open classes (*classi aperte*).

Open Classroom is a web-based, AI-enhanced educational platform conceived to support the personalization of teaching materials, particularly in contexts characterized by varying learning levels, linguistic backgrounds, and special educational needs. The primary functionality of the platform is to enable educators to generate personalized learning materials from a single source document, thereby enhancing inclusivity and teaching effectiveness. By leveraging advances in artificial intelligence, especially large language models (LLMs), Open Classroom assists teachers in producing accessible, level-appropriate content tailored to cognitive, linguistic, and stylistic learning factors. The platform integrates automated text extraction, semantic analysis, and customizable content generation into a unified workflow.

In this section, we outline the conceptual foundations, technical implementation, and functional capabilities of Open Classroom, being developed with a dual objective: (i) enabling the automated transformation of learning materials through AI-driven text processing pipelines, and (ii) supporting teachers' workflows in tailoring such materials to the heterogeneity of learners' profiles.

8.2 Background

8.2.1 Open classes

An open class (*classe aperta*) is an organizational model in which students are not kept in fixed, traditional age-based classroom groups but are instead redistributed flexibly according to learning needs, interests, levels of competence or specific activities. In this approach, students from different sections or grade levels may work together, and groups can change depending on the task at hand. Teachers coordinate their efforts to design activities and reorganize students dynamically. The overall goal is to create a learning environment that is more adaptive, inclusive

and capable of supporting personalized educational pathways by moving beyond the rigid structure of the standard class group.

In a territory like the Aosta Valley, the open class model takes on particular significance because of the region's geographical, demographic and linguistic characteristics. Schools often serve small, dispersed communities, and student groups may be heterogeneous in age, linguistic background and learning needs. Within this context, the open class model provides a flexible way to overcome the limitations of rigid class structures and to manage variability more effectively. By allowing students to be reorganized across sections or even grade levels, teachers can form groups that address specific learning goals, such as reinforcing foundational skills, supporting multilingual learners, or extending activities for more advanced students. This flexibility enables schools within the region to respond to the everyday challenges of mixed-ability classes and small cohorts. It also aligns with the region's emphasis on inclusion and multilingual education, where instruction often needs to be adapted to students with diverse linguistic backgrounds. In this sense, the open class model becomes not only an organizational approach but also a strategic response to the educational needs of a mountainous, multilingual region. It supports more efficient use of teaching resources, promotes collaboration among teachers and helps ensure that every student can access learning pathways suited to their abilities and context.

8.2.2 Large Language Models (LLMs)

Large Language Models (LLMs) represent one of the most significant recent developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly in the field of natural language processing (NLP). These models are trained on vast quantities of textual data and are capable of processing, generating and transforming natural language with a level of fluency that approaches human performance. Their architecture allows them to analyze linguistic patterns, infer contextual meaning, and produce coherent responses or reformulations, making them particularly suitable for tasks such as summarization, translation, simplification and content generation.

In educational contexts, LLMs have gained prominence because they can support multiple stages of the instructional process. They can convert unstructured content into organized textual representations, identifying conceptual relationships within a document, and adapting materials to meet the needs of different learners. Their ability to modulate linguistic complexity, highlight key ideas and restructure information enables educators to create materials that are more accessible to students with diverse cognitive or linguistic profiles.

LLMs operate by processing input prompts, i.e., structured, or unstructured instructions supplied by the user in natural language and generating corresponding outputs that respect the constraints or objectives indicated. The quality and relevance of the output depend heavily on the clarity of the prompt, which has led to the development of specialized techniques known as “prompt engineering.”

Such AI models can play a particularly meaningful role in supporting the open class model. LLMs help address their structural complexity by enabling rapid and consistent adaptation of teaching content: they can simplify or enrich a text depending on the group's competence, modify the format to suit different learning styles, or extract essential concepts to support targeted reinforcement activities. In multilingual contexts such as the Aosta Valley, they can adjust linguistic difficulty or provide parallel explanations that accommodate students with different language repertoires.

Figure 1 General architecture of the Open Classroom platform.

Despite their potential, it is important to emphasize that the use of LLMs in education must be guided by responsible oversight. These models generate content based on patterns in their training data and may reproduce unintended biases or inaccuracies. For this reason, effective human supervision remains essential, particularly when adapting curricular materials or supporting students with specific needs.

8.3 Functional rationale and platform architecture

The rationale behind the Open Classroom platform emerges from the need to support schools that work with small, heterogeneous, and often multilingual student populations. Because open classes require teachers to reorganize students flexibly and to personalize instruction and teaching materials at multiple levels, the platform is designed to streamline this process by offering a structured, AI-assisted workflow that reduces the manual workload typically associated with differentiated teaching. The functional requirements met by the platform are therefore tied to three core needs. First, teachers must be able to transform a single teaching resource into multiple versions that correspond to different learner profiles, such as varying linguistic competence, cognitive levels, or specific educational needs. Second, the adaptations must be consistent, transparent, and modifiable, ensuring that teachers retain complete control over pedagogical decisions. Third, the platform must allow teachers to manage these transformations

quickly and reliably, given that open class configurations may change frequently and require rapid production of tailored materials.

To meet these needs, the architecture of the platform (shown in Figure 1) is organized into distinct but interdependent components. A dedicated space is used to store and manage "profiles", which represent groups of students who share certain learning characteristics. These profiles do not contain personal data but describe relevant traits that guide the personalization process. A second space manages "projects", which are the actual units of work where teachers upload source materials, trigger AI-based analysis, and generate adapted versions. This separation makes it possible to reuse student-group profiles across multiple teaching activities and to maintain clear, customizable workflows.

Behind these interfaces the application encompasses several structured computing layers. One contains the original teaching materials, another captures the intermediate steps and instructional transformations applied by the teacher, and a final one stores the generated personalized outputs. The workflow typically proceeds through automatic extraction of text from the original media, semantic analysis of that text and the creation of personalized versions aligned with selected profiles. At each stage, teachers can inspect, edit and refine the results, thus ensuring that AI functions as an assistant rather than an autonomous decision-maker.

The platform is implemented as a web-based environment using modular, scalable components, in order to make it adaptable to the different digital constraints and infrastructural diversity that characterize educational information systems. It is designed to support multiple large language models (e.g., Open AI's GPT, Google's Gemini, etc.) to allow teachers to choose the most appropriate one for each task. It also allows us to monitor resource consumption so that system usage can remain sustainable.

8.4 Personalization workflow and GUI overview

The personalization workflow is designed to translate the teacher's personalization intentions into concrete, machine-interpretable instructions for the AI models, ensuring that the generated materials reflect the specific needs of the groups involved in an open class setting. This process begins when the teacher interacts with the graphical interface to define two types of information: the characteristics of the student profiles and the goals or constraints of the project. These inputs include factors such as age, learning level, linguistic competence, preferred learning modalities, presence of special educational needs and the intended structure or depth of the final materials. Although the teacher expresses these elements intuitively through selections, text fields or toggles in the interface, the system internally reformulates them into a sequence of highly structured and coherent prompts.

This transformation is a crucial stage of the workflow. Rather than sending raw or loosely formulated instructions to the AI, the platform interprets each user selection and translates it into a prompt segment carefully engineered for the specific step of the process. The extraction step,

for example, uses a prompt focused on recovering text faithfully from the media source while applying any initial adaptations required by the selected profiles. The semantic-analysis step employs a different structure, guiding the model to identify key concepts, logical sections and lexical difficulties. The generation step uses even more detailed prompts, incorporating all profile-related parameters to produce personalized teaching content that is consistent and aligned with the teacher's intentions.

Figure 2 Landing page for the teacher.

Once the platform constructs these prompts, the AI models execute them sequentially. Each step produces text that serves as the input for the next stage. The output of the extraction step provides the basis for semantic interpretation; the results of semantic analysis, in turn, guide the generation of differentiated versions. At every stage, the teacher retains the ability to read, evaluate and modify the text produced by the AI, adding manual adjustments where necessary. The final personalized materials emerge from this interplay between teacher-defined parameters, automated prompt engineering and LLM execution. The system compiles the generated text into structured documents, optionally reinserting images extracted from the original media and supporting export in various formats suitable for distribution. By orchestrating the workflow in this way, the platform makes it possible to generate multiple tailored versions of a resource rapidly and with high internal consistency.

In the following, we briefly describe each step of the personalization workflow.

8.4.1 Access to the project space

Figure 2 shows the landing page where the teacher can create a new project or access previously developed ones. The dashboard also displays the available LLMs, the number of tokens currently

remaining for each model and the historical consumption associated with completed projects. This information helps the teacher assess the resources required and estimate whether sufficient capacity is available to continue with further processing. At the top of the page, the teacher can select the language of the graphical interface as well as the language used for prompts and for the generated responses.

The screenshot shows the 'Project Space' interface in the 'Open Classroom' application. At the top, there are navigation elements including the 'Open Classroom' logo, the 'Project Space' title, a language dropdown set to 'English', a user profile for 'Mario Rossi', and a 'Logout' button. Below this is a progress bar with five steps: 'Media Import & Profile Selection' (active), 'Media to Text', 'Text to Segmented Text', 'Segmented Text to Teaching Material', and 'Export Final Materials'. The main content area is a form for project setup. It includes a 'Project Name' field with the value 'Napoleon-Background_20251114_174325'. Below that is a 'Change file (optional)' section showing the current file 'Napoleon-Background.pdf' and a dashed box for uploading new media with the text 'Click to browse or drop your Media here'. The 'Select Student Profiles' section contains a grid of 12 profile selection buttons. Two profiles are selected: 'Profile1_Age12_Dyslexia' and 'Profile1_Age6_None'. A 'Next -->' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 3 First step of the personalization workflow.

Figure 3, in turn, shows the first step of the personalization workflow, where the teacher uploads the source material and selects the profiles to be used for personalization.

8.4.2 Creation of new projects and profiles

To start a new project, the teacher follows a guided creation page. They first import source media (for example a document, slide deck, or other teaching material). Then they select at least one student profile, typically all profiles corresponding to their open class. The application proposes a default project name (derived from the media), which the teacher may modify before proceeding. Within the application, a profile is a structured description of a group of students who share similar learning characteristics. Profiles are stored as structured data and include several dimensions that influence how the AI adapts content. Among these dimensions are the age range or general developmental level of the group, which determines the complexity of

vocabulary and depth of explanations appropriate for that profile. They also include the language of learning, which is particularly relevant in multilingual regions and affects both the linguistic register and the language in which materials are produced.

The screenshot displays the 'Project Space' interface for 'Open Classroom'. At the top, there are navigation elements including the language 'English', the user 'Mario Rossi', and a 'Logout' button. A progress bar indicates five steps: 'Media Import & Profile Selection', 'Media to Text', 'Text to Segmented Text' (the current step), 'Segmented Text to Teaching Material', and 'Export Final Materials'. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Tips & Instructions:** A box providing guidance on adding supplementary instructions, selecting an AI model, and clicking 'AI Generation' to create extracted key concepts and segmentation.
- Imported Media:** A list showing 'Napoleon-Background.pdf' as imported media.
- Selected Profiles:** A list of profiles including 'Profile1_Age12_Dyslexia' and 'Profile1_Age6_None'.
- Supplementary Instructions (Optional):** A text area for adding additional instructions for analysis, such as focusing on specific topics or including particular details.
- AI Model:** A dropdown menu set to 'Gemini 2.0' and an 'AI Generation' button.
- Extracted Key Concepts and Segmentation:** A large text area displaying the results of the AI process, including a list of 'CONCETTI CHIAVE' (Key Concepts) and 'SEGMENTAZIONE DEL CONTENUTO' (Content Segmentation).

At the bottom of the interface, there are 'Previous' and 'Next' navigation buttons.

Figure 4 Text segmentation phase.

Another key component is the indication of special educational needs. Profiles also specify the disciplinary area relevant to the students, helping the system tailor examples, terminology and

conceptual framing. Additionally, profiles reflect the students' preferred learning styles, such as visual, auditory or text-based preferences. This information influences the way content is organized, whether through bullet-point summaries, concept maps, reorganized explanations or more linear textual narratives.

Teachers have full control over the creation and modification of profiles, allowing them to shape these descriptors in the way that best suits their instructional needs. Although profiles are designed to represent groups rather than individual students, the platform gives teachers the flexibility to adjust every component of a profile so that it reflects the real learning characteristics of the groups they work with. This means that teachers can define new profiles from scratch when their class composition changes, when they introduce new forms of grouping in open class activities or when they need to target specific pedagogical goals. They can edit existing profiles by updating learning levels, linguistic information, preferred learning styles or indications of special educational needs, ensuring that the personalization process always aligns with the most up-to-date understanding of their students.

Because the platform stores profiles independently from individual projects, any modification made by a teacher becomes immediately available for all future projects.

The project then proceeds through a sequence of steps. The teacher can interrupt the work and later resume from the last saved step. They can also re-run a step or go back to a previous one to make changes, so the workflow is linear in structure but remains fully revisable.

8.4.3 Media-to-text extraction

In the first processing step, the system extracts text from the uploaded media. That text becomes the basis for all subsequent analysis and generation.

At this point, the teacher can:

- Add or refine instructions in the prompt.
- Edit the extracted or generated text directly in the interface.
- Choose which LLM engine to use.

8.4.4 Text analysis and segmentation

In the next step, shown in Figure 4, the application analyses the text. The LLM receives a prompt tailored to identify key concepts, important terms and a logical segmentation of the content into sections or units that are pedagogically meaningful. Again, the teacher can add specific instructions to the prompt and select the preferred LLM. The output is a textual analysis that appears on screen, which the teacher can read and, if necessary, modify. This analyzed and segmented text provides the structure on which the personalized teaching materials will be built.

Figure 5 Personalized material generation.

8.4.5 Generation of personalized teaching materials

In the following step (Figure 5), the teacher asks the system to generate the personalized teaching materials. Before launching generation, they can once more adjust the prompt and choose the LLM. At this stage, the system makes full use of the specific information contained in the selected profiles. The LLM produces text versions tailored to each profile, for example with simplified language, adapted structure or different depth of explanation. The teacher sees these versions in the interface, can compare them, edit the text, and iterate until satisfied.

Figure 6 Final material export phase.

8.4.6 Export and finalization

In the ultimate step, shown in Figure 6, the personalized teaching material, so far managed as text is transformed into distributable file formats. The system can generate .docx and .pdf versions and automatically reinsert images taken from the original media at the end of the document. The teacher can then download or store the exported materials. This completes the project workflow for that set of profiles and media.

8.5 Expected impact

From an organizational perspective, the platform is designed and expected to produce a significant and measurable impact on the management and daily functioning of open classes. Open class settings require teachers to reorganize groups frequently, adapt materials to heterogeneous learners and collaborate across subjects or sections. These activities, while pedagogically valuable, create a substantial operational burden. The platform directly addresses this challenge by providing an integrated environment in which teachers can generate, modify and distribute personalized materials efficiently. By automating the most time-consuming phases of adaptation, such as text extraction, semantic analysis and personalization, the system streamlines the entire preparatory workflow, freeing teachers to focus on instructional design, monitoring of students and collaborative planning.

In addition to simplifying material preparation, the platform introduces a data-driven layer to the management of open classes. By tracking resource usage, project frequency, iteration patterns and the level of personalization applied, the system can offer analytical insights into how teachers work, how often certain adaptations are required and where AI contributes most effectively to their productivity. These insights can help both teachers, schools and administrators better understand the operational dynamics of open classes and plan support measures, training initiatives, or teaching strategies accordingly.

Moreover, by capturing the interaction between teacher-driven choices and AI-generated outputs, the platform helps illustrate how artificial intelligence can enhance not only efficiency but also the overall quality of teaching practices in flexible learning environments. Over time, the accumulated data can contribute to evidence-based evaluations of how AI tools improve material accessibility, enable more responsive grouping strategies and support multilingual or inclusive education.

In this way, the Open Classroom platform is expected to act not only as a practical tool for teachers but also as a strategic organizational instrument for schools. It promotes an organizational culture that embraces technological innovation while maintaining strong human oversight, improving the sustainability, consistency and coherence of open class models.

8.6 Limitations and future work

While the current platform prototype already provides a robust foundation for supporting open class teaching, several limitations remain that point towards opportunities for future development. At present, the system focuses primarily on the generation of text-based materials. Although the workflow can reinsert images from the original media, fully multimodal output, such as audio narration, AI-generated visual elements or interactive digital formats, has not yet been implemented. This limits the range of adaptations available for younger learners or students who benefit from more visual or multisensory instructional supports.

From an evaluation standpoint, the system does not yet include built-in instruments for collecting student feedback on the personalized materials they receive. The future roadmap includes adding to the final generated materials automatically generated evaluation forms. These questionnaires would assess the appropriateness and effectiveness of the adaptations for each student profile. This represents a major step towards data-informed personalization.

Concerning the quantitative evaluation dimension, in future iterations, teachers will have access to a rich analytical dashboard, including metrics such as token usage, number of projects created, number of personalized documents produced, the frequency of modifications or regenerations, the volume of teacher-initiated edits, unresolved requests, time-to-completion of projects and longitudinal reuse trends. This data will help them better understand their workflow and will support schools in evaluating the organizational benefits of AI-assisted personalization.

A fundamental element of future work will be on-field testing of the platform with a selected group of teachers. While the platform has been designed with real classroom dynamics in mind, its full effectiveness can only be assessed through direct use in open class settings. Engaging a small cohort of teachers in structured pilot testing will make it possible to observe how the workflow integrates into everyday teaching practices, how easily the personalization tools are adopted and where the process requires refinement. This phase will also allow developers to gather practical insights on usability, token consumption, typical project structures, and the actual value of the generated materials for heterogeneous groups. Importantly, teachers' feedback during this pilot phase will guide the prioritization of further improvements, ensuring that the platform evolves in close alignment with the practical needs of schools in the Aosta Valley.

I) Expected scenarios in education

On January 12, 2026, a workshop entitled "Digital and Sustainable Northwest Project using PNRR funds - Investigation of Innovative Teaching Models - Online workshop to present the AI-supported teaching platform in open classrooms" was held. The primary objective of the event was to introduce the advanced AI prototype platform—described in the previous two paragraphs—to key stakeholders outside UNIVDA (the Aosta Valley Superintendency of Studies, the institutional sponsor of the project, and the heads of Aosta Valley schools). The other objectives of the workshop, no less important for the research group, were to: return the final step of the research project to the institutional stakeholders involved from the beginning; test stakeholder satisfaction with the construction and outcomes of the final phase of the research, in order to implement field trials; Expand the scope of field trials beyond the schools participating in the initial phases (also to increase the number of stakeholders responding to the questionnaires administered in the early stages of the field research).

But the most significant project objective was to "strengthen" the alliance with the local community and with stakeholders potentially interested in the research project, in order to build fertile ground for the future. This appears to be part of the overall institutional mission and vision of the NODES - Digital and Sustainable North West

SPOKE 4 - Digital and Sustainable Mountain Project, as well as, of course, in the section "A model for innovative education in mountain areas combining digital technology, environmental education, and outdoor learning."

The Workshop fulfills the objectives described but can also serve as a "grounding" point for the project, reflecting on and envisioning the future of research action. The education sector and the Public Management approach are currently receiving significant attention in Italy (where the central government has proactively relaunched and regulated action on innovation in teaching, digitalization, and the use of AI, continuing into the second half of 2025, confirming and

reinforcing the Project's research principles). Furthermore, other key institutional actors, considered institutional stakeholders capable of exerting authoritative moral suasion, are also expressing their opinion on the need for innovation, investment—including economic investment—and attention to the education sector and its Public Management approaches.

According to Panetta, Governor of the Bank of Italy¹ and former ECB Executive Board member, Italy must increase spending on education and knowledge, especially higher education, which generates "high economic and social returns," if it wants to keep pace with technological change and ensure "stable growth," especially given the demographic decline. The Governor of the Bank of Italy chose the inauguration ceremony of the 2025-2026 academic year at the University of Messina to return to the topic of the country's competitiveness and growth, a combination that can only be achieved by cultivating tomorrow's knowledge. It is no coincidence that his inaugural address is titled "Investing in the future: young people, innovation, and human capital."

According to Panetta, targeted support for families and education generates high economic and social returns: "The measures can be implemented gradually, preserving prudent management of public finances and the progress made in reducing the cost of debt". Public resources allocated to education are less than 4% of GDP, almost one point less than the EU average and the lowest level among the main economies of the euro area, Panetta recalls.

His positions emphasize that while specific workshops fulfill immediate technical or policy objectives, they also serve as a broader vehicle for:

- Investing in Human Capital: Panetta argues that growth in the Euro area and Italy depends on increasing youth and women's employment to close participation gaps.
- Fostering Innovation: He points out a significant "innovation gap" where European firms invest only half as much as U.S. firms in research and development, particularly among young, innovative companies.
- Addressing Skills Gaps: To maintain competitiveness, he advocates for structural reforms in education and training to provide the skilled workforce needed for digital and green transitions.
- European Integration: Panetta posits that deeper European integration is the best defense against global fragmentation, providing the scale necessary to support large-scale innovation and collective security.

Panetta concluded his report² by stating, "Investing in education, research, and training thus means investing both in the country's potential and in the aspirations of individuals: in the ability

¹ Il Sole 24 Ore, 15 gennaio 2026, Bankitalia, Panetta: 'Puntare sul capitale umano. Un giovane laureato tedesco guadagna l'80% in più di un italiano.

² <https://www.bancaditalia.it/pubblicazioni/interventi-governatore/integov2026/20260115-panetta/index.html?dotcache=refresh>

of young people to choose, to grow, to contribute to a more dynamic economy and a more just society”.

It is on this combination of knowledge and innovation, of individual commitment and the quality of institutions, that the progress of our societies in the contemporary era is based.”

Ultimately, it is possible to argue that starting from the initial research postulates, the field analysis, integrated with the construction of the prototype platform, sequentially confirms the desired, modeled, and proposed innovation needs. The theme of digitalization and the use of AI in innovative teaching models—open classrooms—with the linchpin of public management paradigms, are fundamental humus for continuing to study, contextualize, propose, and experiment with models that yield the desired results.

Artificial Intelligence has the potential to revolutionize education by offering personalized learning experiences, automating administrative tasks, and supporting teachers in identifying student needs. Immersive technologies such as virtual reality are already commonly used to teach technical skills and are also being explored to develop soft skills such as empathy. However, the implementation of these technologies in education also raises concerns about data privacy, equity, and the potential for bias. A major challenge, even as the project's research continues, is understanding how educational systems can leverage AI and other cutting-edge technologies to enhance learning, while addressing these ethical and practical challenges.

Another key issue in the near future is the implementation of education policies based on the principles of equity and access: the digital divide remains a significant obstacle to the equitable use of AI and technology in educational institutions and for different stakeholders. Ensuring that all teachers, students, and parents, depending on their level of involvement or cooperation with the educational service, have access to the necessary tools and resources is essential to promoting an inclusive educational environment. A key issue for the future of the Project, in accordance with OECD recommendations³, may concern the question of how educational systems with open classroom models can bridge the digital divide and ensure that the benefits of artificial intelligence and technology extend to all students in these models.

J) Research trajectories for the future

Compared to the initial Road Map, the project was developed by adding, along the way, the final phase of building a prototype AI platform (see the previous sections for a better explanation of this phase). This toolkit, initially designed for teachers—a fundamental part of the core service—but which also takes into account, within the platform itself, specific management and organizational tools to support the decisions of educational institutions and individual teachers,

³ Trends Shaping Education 2025, OECD.

can be instrumental, already in the experimentation phase, in determining the degree of interaction between actors in the educational process at different levels of governance.

First, it is essential to have the space and resources to maintain and manage coalition-building efforts among institutional stakeholders in the education sector. Second, given the positive reception during the final workshop, it is essential to test the prototype platform to understand its functioning in the field and work to resolve any critical issues. We also need to analyse any new aspects of innovation and development that emerge from the testing, so as to offer concrete organizational and management tools in the local area.

Secondly, it would be appropriate to broaden the scope of the research for a wider comparison at the national and international level, which, one imagines, is significant given the extreme topicality of the research action.

In particular, the aim is to enhance the Project's starting point. We started from a specific characteristic: the use of the multi-grade model, typically for reasons related to scarce resources (staff, logistics, time). Field analysis observed a growing sensitivity among school managers and teachers to the open-class model. It would be very challenging to combine the feasibility of teaching models linked to the evolution of the open-class model with the support of digital and AI across multiple grade levels and multiple types of schools.

Third, it is considered appropriate to build strategic alliances at the national and supranational levels to consolidate spaces for discussion that will foster stability and consistency in research on topics considered to be highly accelerating in terms of innovation and change.

The fourth area, more concretely connected to the research topics, concerns the belief that it is essential to fully explore the relationship between innovative teaching models—typically the different open class formats and the different variations/verticalizations—their application in specific institutional contexts, the role of the various actors—political decision-makers, managers, teachers, administrative functions, parents, and, of course, at the centre—students (also by further expanding and detailing the questions in the questionnaires already administered). Ultimately, starting from the research's final outputs—the proposal of a digital innovation and AI prototype to support the teacher-student relationship, but also to broaden the relationship to other internal and external stakeholders—the intention is to apply the stakeholder engagement model to create harmony in the relationship between the actors who decide, produce, and use educational services in the context of digitalization and the delivery of educational services themselves.